

Predicting Earth Magnetic Anomalies from Measured EMAG2 Data

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Abstract—Magnetic anomaly maps are important for scientific and practical applications; such as they provide insight into the subsurface structure and composition of the Earth's terrestrial and oceanic crusts. These maps are widely applicable for geological exploration and detection of man-made subsurface anomalies. There is available high-resolution 2 arc-minute global Earth Magnetic Anomaly Grid data (EMAG2) at 4 km above the geoid [1], which has been created using various satellite, ship, and airborne magnetic measurements. However, many, if not all, practical applications require EMAG data at different elevations and different resolutions. To achieve this demand here EMAG2 data at 4 km elevation is remapped at different elevations and resolutions using the method of auxiliary sources. Comparisons between predicted and measured data are demonstrated.

Index Terms—Magnetic anomalies; MAS; Detection; Models; EMAG; Geology.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Earth's magnetic field has been used for subsurface structure studies, geophysical exploration, detection of man-made target and navigation [1-4]. The latter has continued to improve alongside transportation technologies and now days accurate earth magnetic models are used in planes, ships and even smartphones, particularly in GPS denied areas. Therefore, there is a need to develop very accurate models for mapping Earth magnetic anomalies at different elevations and resolutions. To overcome this problem, in this paper first, the method of auxiliary sources (AS) is applied to EMAG2 data set, then the magnitude of AS are predicted and used for estimating field at any point in the space.

The Method of Auxiliary Sources (MAS) is a numerical technique originally designed for solving various electromagnetic radiation and scattering problems [5]. The MAS is robust, easy to implement, and accurate, and has been used to investigate waveguide structures, antennas, scattering, electromagnetic wave propagation in complex media, etc. It

has also been employed successfully in the analysis of low-frequency electromagnetic induction scattering phenomena [5]. In the MAS, boundary value problems are solved numerically by representing the electromagnetic fields in each domain of the structure under investigation by a finite linear combination of analytical solutions of the relevant field equations, corresponding to sources situated at some distance away from the boundaries of each domain. The “auxiliary sources” producing these analytical solutions are chosen to be elementary dipoles/charges located on fictitious auxiliary surfaces that usually conform to the actual surface(s) of the structure. In practice, at least as the method is realized here, we only require points on the auxiliary and actual surfaces; thus we do not need to the detailed mesh structures required by other methods.

The two auxiliary surfaces are set up inside and outside the scattering object. The fields outside of the structure are considered to originate from a set of auxiliary magnetic charges placed inside the object, while the fields inside the object are taken to arise from a set of auxiliary magnetic dipoles placed outside. The interior and exterior fields thus constructed are required to obey Maxwell's boundary conditions—the continuity of the tangential magnetic field components and the jump condition for the normal magnetic field components—as evaluated at arrays of selected points on the physical surface(s) of the structure. This results in a matrix equation in which the amplitudes of the auxiliary sources are the unknowns to be determined. Once these amplitudes are found the solution is complete: the electromagnetic field—as well as any quantity related to it—can easily be computed throughout the computational space.

The MAS formulation we present here offers a number of advantages. It is no longer necessary to perform integrations to generate an algebraic system. Field singularities at source locations need not be confronted directly, since the auxiliary

surfaces containing the sources are separated from the physical surface where the conditions are evaluated. In the simplest MAS formulation no discretization of either the surfaces or volumes of interest is required; all we need to know are the locations of the observation (testing) points on the real surface and the locations of the sources on the auxiliary surfaces.

II. NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE MAS FOR EMAG

In the ensuing analysis we consider that the surface of the body is smooth. There are two auxiliary surfaces and that these are positioned inside and outside the physical surface ∂D of the target. The real (physical) surface ∂D is divided into M subsurfaces. For each m^{th} subsurface, a location point \mathbf{r}_m , the surface normal there $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_m$, and the surface tangential vectors $\hat{\mathbf{s}}_m$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_m$ are determined using $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_m = [\hat{\mathbf{t}}_m \times \hat{\mathbf{s}}_m]$. The secondary field in region 1, on and outside the earth surface, due to the magnetic anomalies will be generated by N magnetic point charges, $\{Q_n\}$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$, placed on the surface ∂D_1 at the points \mathbf{r}_{1n} . We emphasize that this auxiliary surface is enclosed by the physical surface ∂D , (earth surface) and these charges $\{Q_n\}$ radiate as if in an unbounded free space, giving rise to the magnetic field \mathbf{H} , which may be represented at point \mathbf{r}_m as

$$\mathbf{H}^{\text{sc}}(\mathbf{r}_m) = \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{G}_Q(m, n) = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{Q_n}{4\pi\mu_0} \frac{(\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_{1n})}{|\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_{1n}|^3}, \quad (1)$$

with $\mathbf{r}_m \in \partial D$ and $\mathbf{r}_{1n} \in \partial D_1$, where $\mathbf{G}_Q(m, n)$, the magnetic field due to a magnetic charge source Q_n placed at point \mathbf{r}_{1n} and evaluated at \mathbf{r}_m is obtained by taking the gradient of a scalar potential satisfying Poisson's equation.

In order to reduce the number of unknowns and obtain a highly accurate field representation, the problem was modeled using bodies of revolution (BOR). While a BOR is ultimately three-dimensional and produces 3D scattered fields, its rotational symmetry reduces the computational problem to 2.5D. Details of typical BOR formulations for other techniques, such as MAS and the Method of Moments (MoM), appear in the references [5-10]. Here we indicate only the particular expressions required in terms of auxiliary sources. Consider a conducting and permeable BOR formed by rotating a generating line about the z -axis of a Cartesian coordinate system and placed in a time-harmonic primary magnetic field (which need not itself be rotationally symmetric). The azimuthal dependence of the fields is expressed via a Fourier series, whose modes $\exp(jL\phi)$ are used to include all rotational variation. Since the azimuthal field variation is analytically accounted for, no boundary condition matching

points are distributed in the azimuthal $\hat{\phi}$ direction. The resulting sets of simultaneous equations may be represented in matrix form as

$$[Z^L][I^L] = [V^L], \text{ for } L = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \pm 3, \dots \quad (2)$$

where $[Z^L]$ is the impedance matrix for the L -th Fourier mode, I^L is a column vector containing the unknown amplitude of the auxiliary sources for the L -th Fourier mode, and $[V^L]$ is the measured EMAG2 at 4 km elevation i.e. driving vector for the L -th Fourier mode. The $\mathbf{H}(\mathbf{r}_m)$, can be generated by the sources from N auxiliary belts through

$$\mathbf{H}^{\text{sc}}(\mathbf{r}_m) = \sum_{n=1}^N \mathbf{G}_Q^{\phi}(m, n), \quad (3)$$

where in (3)

$$\mathbf{G}_Q^{\phi}(m, n) = \frac{1}{4\pi\mu_0} \sum_{i\phi=1}^{N_{\phi}(n)} \frac{Q_n(\phi)}{|\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_{1n, i\phi}|} (\mathbf{r}_m - \mathbf{r}_{1n, i\phi}) \quad (4)$$

is the scattering magnetic field in region 1 (outside earth) at the point \mathbf{r}_m produced by a magnetic charge $Q_n(\phi)$ distributed on the n^{th} inner auxiliary belt (ring) at $\mathbf{r}_{1n, i\phi} = \rho_{1n}(\hat{\mathbf{x}} \cos \phi_{i\phi} + \hat{\mathbf{y}} \sin \phi_{i\phi}) + \hat{\mathbf{z}} z_{1n}$, where ρ_{1n} is the belt's radius and $N_{\phi}(n)$ is the number of azimuthal points on the belt.

For the BOR problem at hand, we include the ϕ dependence of \mathbf{H}^{pr} and $Q_n(\phi)$ in (4) by expanding them in Fourier series in ϕ :

$$Q_n(\phi) = \sum_{L=0}^{\infty} (Q_{n,L}^t \cos(L\phi) + Q_{n,L}^{\phi} \sin(L\phi)) \quad (5)$$

where L is the mode number, and $\mathbf{H}_{t,L}^{\text{pr}}$, $\mathbf{H}_{\phi,L}^{\text{pr}}$, $Q_{n,L}^t$, and $Q_{n,L}^{\phi}$ are the Fourier coefficients. These coefficients are dependent only on ρ and z and according to rotational symmetry they are constant on each belt (ring).

Finally, the formulation is achieved by substituting (5) and (3), so that the magnetic $\mathbf{H}_1^{\text{sc}}(\mathbf{r}_m)$ field at \mathbf{r}_m from all Fourier modes can be represented as

$$\mathbf{H}_1^{\text{sc}}(\mathbf{r}_m) = \sum_{L=0}^{\infty} \left\{ \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{n,L}^t \mathbf{G}_{1Q}^{\phi}(m, n, L) + \sum_{n=1}^N Q_{n,L}^{\phi} \mathbf{G}_{2Q}^{\phi}(m, n, L) \right\}, \quad (6)$$

Figure 1. Interpolated Earth Magnetic Anomaly Grid Data over entire earth surface at 4 km above sea level [1].

So, for remapping earth magnetic anomalies at any point, first EMAG2 data must be decomposed into cos and sin modes, then boundary value problems must be solved for each mode and finally, magnetic fields can be represented by summing the fields produced by all cos and sin modes.

III. RESULTS

Here we used the earth magnetic anomaly grid data at 2 arc-minute resolution (EMAG2). These data were compiled from satellite, ship, and airborne magnetic measurements at 4 km above the sea level. The EMAG2 is a significant high resolution and accurate data sets compared to alternatives such as the World Digital Magnetic Anomaly Map. Namely, its resolution has been improved from 3 arc-minutes to 2 arc-minutes, and the altitude has been reduced from 5 km to 4 km above the geoid [1]. In addition, new grid and track line data have been included, both over land and the oceans. Wherever available, the original shipborne and airborne data were used instead of precompiled oceanic magnetic grids [1]. The interpolated data over the entire earth is depicted in Figure 1. We took these data and decomposed into Fourier modes along ϕ coordinate on the sphere. The comparisons between estimated and actual EMAG2 data set versus longitude at 4 km elevation are shown in Figure 2. There is a perfect match between predicted and actual data. The model had 2500 Fourier modes.

Figure 2. Comparisons: between actual and estimated fields using Fourier decomposition at 4 km.

Figure 3. Green line: Actual EMAG2 at 4 km vs observation points and Red line: estimated using the MAS at sea level.

To predict fields due to earth magnetic anomalies for each Fourier modes, we solved the requisite boundary value problem and calculated the magnitudes of AS by matching modeled field to the EMAG2 data at 4 km elevations. Once the magnitudes of AS were determined then the field was predicted on a given point. The predicted magnetic field at sea level vs observation points is depicted in Figure 3, red line. The comparison between the predicted and actual measured EMAG2 data shows that the magnetic field at sea level is slightly higher than at 4 km elevation as expected, and the predicted spatial variation features are similar to the field distribution at higher elevation. Thus, these results indicate that the MAS is an applicable technique for EMAG2 data prediction.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper the MAS was applied to earth magnetic field anomalies gridded data set. First, EMAG2 data were decomposed into Fourier modes; then, for each mode the boundary value problem was solved and the magnitudes of AS

were estimated. Finally, the estimated AS were used and EMAG2 data was predicted at different elevations. The comparisons between actual EMAG2 and predicted data indicate that the MAS is a valuable technique for remapping EMAG data at any point in the space on/or above earth surface.

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